

Geo-cultural Interventions in Cross-Civilizational Communication Towards a Dialogical Approach

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Abstract

Current epistemic themes, e.g., geo-culture, capture the epistemological injustices and power imbalances inherent in conventional IR discourses; the emergence of geo-culture is exacerbated by the resurgence of the populist-nationalist resistance to “Western” universal values and the rise of clashism (i.e. Clash of Civilizations thesis) which is nurtured by narratives of cultural irreconcilability. This chapter speaks of the need to rethink and contest the post-bipolar discourses (e.g., the clash theory and the end of history rhetoric) that sustained inter-civilizational tensions and disputes. It proposes geo-culture as an alternative lens through which inter-civilizational relations/encounters may be envisaged. The rationale is to engage with counter-hegemonic discourses that challenge the essentialist and monolithic framings of East-West relations and that promote dialogue, pluralism and co-existence. The chapter therefore seeks to: (a) lay out a conceptual framework for the emergence of geo-culture, along with its intersection with soft power (b) make a case for ‘dialogue among civilizations’ as an antidote to the clash theory and (c) draw on the philosophical insights of three authorities (Hans-George Gadamer (1975), Va’clav Havel (1994) and Bassam Tibi, 2012)—all of whom stand in favour of human dialogue and cross-civilizational pollination.

Keywords: geo-culture; cross-civilizational communication; inter-civilizational conflict; inter-civilizational dialogue.

1. Introduction

The post-bipolar international society has entered an era of multicultural and multipolar world order that requires devising an intellectual and peaceful framework committed to fertilizing a cross-cultural landscape of mutual dialogue in the context of inter-civilizational encounters¹. Notwithstanding, the politics underlying the post-Cold War discourse has been informed by two main notorious theses of the century—namely Francis Fukuyama’s ‘End of History’ and Samuel Huntington’s ‘Clash of Civilizations’. Both theories endorse a philosophy of a unilateral and mono-logical politics of world order reflecting solely Western-centric civilizational and liberal models. Against these discourses, dialogue of civilizations is proposed by international relations theorists (e.g. Fred Dallmayr, 2009; Mohammed Khatami, 1998)² as an alternative discourse for mono-cultural or civilizational international coexistence. The latter stresses the importance of establishing the core tenets of dialogue for pursuing a cross-civilizational mutual understanding and mitigating the risks of what Fabio Petito called ‘culturalist enclosure—that is, the essentialization of cultural and civilizational differences. By a way of illustration, the critical stance of the dialogical paradigm is to problematize and re-examine the core Western-centric liberal and political assumptions upon which cross-civilizational relations are based. In the same line of argument, geo-cultural philosophy—a third prism of international relations that emphasizes the return of cultural and religious to the public square—rethinks the way cultural pluralism is dealt with in cross-cultural interactions, questions the extent to which under-represented civilizations and cultures are valorized in the discourse of the cultural politics of international and intercultural relations and embraces an epistemological polylogue of cross-civilizational discourse. Geo-culture is, moreover, dialogical in nature as it seeks to envisage bridges for mutual cross-cultural/civilizational understanding at multiple

levels—the topmost civilizational relations. To this end, the present chapter takes the stance against the mono-logical discourses underpinning inter-civilizational encounters and the essentialist conceptualizations of world cultures/ civilizations in academic discourse. In doing so, it equates the geo-cultural paradigm with the dialogical theory in terms of points of convergence and discusses their underlying objectives in reference to inter-cultural/civilization communication and politics of international world order.

2. Theorizing Geo-culture: A conceptual Framework

The emergence of geo-culture, as a nascent paradigm, marks the cultural turn underlying the study of international relations (IRs) scholarship. However, before its inception, a large body of intellectual work has been written on geo-economics and geo-politics to explore complex and pending cultural and political issues governing international communication across diverse cultural and civilizational polities. While the geo-economics approach attempts to ascertain disputes across cultures and civilizations from an economic perspective, the geo-politics or basically critical geo-politics approach addresses these conflicts from a political lens. As such, each paradigm adopts specific schemes of reference in order to deconstruct the cultural, ideological and political discourses and epistemes governing international cultural relations. That said, this section outlines the core tenets of the two paradigms envisaging international relations—namely geo-economics and geo-politics and unravels their drawbacks, which eventually induced scholars to frame international relations from a third paradigm—that is geo-culture.

Since its inception into the study of international relations, geo-economics has gained some attention in the research circles (Fiori³, 2008; Strange, 1970)⁴. It was first introduced by Edward Luttwak in 1990s in his seminal article “From Geopolitics to Geo-economics: Logic of Conflict, Grammar of Commerce”, pointing out that Post-Cold war political and cultural discourses will be sparked by economic factors rather than political or military ones⁵. In the tradition of Luttwak, geo-economics is viewed as a form of power implemented for pursuing strategic goals, realizing political agendas and imposing cultural assets. Hudson et al. (1991)⁶, for example, perceive geo-economics as strategies of territorial control that are economically motivated and carried out by economic means, the most

important of which are investment and trade. In another definition put forward by Harris et al (2016, p. 24), “geo-economics is a parallel account of how a state builds and exercises power by reference to economic factors”.⁷

On the other hand, non-Luttwakian scholars regard geo-economics as a discourse, informing the agendas and policies of think-tanks and policy-makers (Sören and Mikael, 2018)⁸. For them, geo-economics discourse is used as a soft power tool whereby countries conduct and legitimize their cultural hegemony and political interests. Therefore, such kind of narratives are monological par excellence, thus curbing the plurality of perspectives and polylogical cultural representations in world politics. Against this background, weaving a discourse of cooperation and dialogue across cultures is central to meeting the demands of our globe which is marked by the diversity of cultures, civilizations and religions.

Geo-politics, on the other hand, is another theory of international relations. It was coined in 1899 by the Swedish political scientist Rudolf Kjellen, defining it as “the theory of the state as a geographical organism or phenomenon in space” (Cohen, 2001).⁹ In a similar context, Sprout and Sprout¹⁰ (1960) maintain that in classical academic theorization, geo-politics comes to deal with the physical environment (location, resources, territory, etc.) and the conduct of foreign policy. In a more refined conceptualization of the meaning of geo-politics, Ó Tuathali and Agnew (1992, p. 4) understand it “as a discursive practice by which intellectuals of statecraft ‘spatialize’ international politics in such a way as to represent it a ‘world’ characterized by particular types of places, peoples and dramas”.¹¹ By incorporating the notion of discourse into the analysis of geo-politics, Ó Tuathail and Agnew argue that geo-politics analyzes the socio-cultural resources, rules and practices whereby intellectuals of statecraft—such as foreign-policy experts, advisors and various public think-tanks—design, articulate and order foreign

policies at the governmental level or implement particular foreign policies and practise statecraft on a daily basis.

By contrast, critical geo-politics has emerged as a school of thought to question and deconstruct the discourses of international politics and conceptualize geopolitics as a social, cultural and political practice. As a research endeavour, it seeks to unpack how popular cultural assumptions and artistic representations—such as literature, journalistic media, government communications and other rhetorical strategies—about geography and politics formulate contemporary discourses and ontologies about the cultural/ civilizational Other (Toal and Dably, 1998)¹².

Loosely put, despite the worthwhile contributions advanced by geo-economics and geo-politics to the discussion on how countries sustain their cultural, political and economic dominance by means of economic and political policies, yet both approaches failed to pay heed to the significance of culture and religion in perpetuating ideological and hegemonic discourses about the cultural Other in world politics. In view of this, the geo-cultural theory emerged to address this lacuna.

The geo-cultural paradigm, which has received a scant attention in the literature of international cultural relations, capitalizes on the impact of a specific culture on inter-cultural/ civilizational communication. It was used for the first time by Immanuel Wallerstein in 1991¹³ in his book “Geo-politics and Geo-culture: Essays on the Changing World Systems” to refer to the cultural framework within which the world-system operates, speculating that states are in incessant dialectical positions over remaking of the world system along with their cultural, civilizational and religious models. For Wallerstein, the world-system is composed of three sub-systems: the economic and political structure and the symbolic and cultural structure. The latter structure is geo-culture.

It is worth-noting that geo-culture has only been given some attention in the tradition of cross-cultural and civilizational communication since Samuel Huntington's release of his notorious and thought-provoking thesis of 'clash of civilizations'. Since then, inter-civilizational conflicts have been explained in light of the geo-cultural theory—the latter has paved the way for a plethora of themes and areas underdeveloped by geo-economics and geo-politics.

In a recent article, Gaumgaumi (2021)¹⁴ defines geo-culture as the combination of what is cultural and what is geographic by way of intercultural communication and international relations. It is about how what is the cultural (ideas, rituals, objects) get distributed across geography (space). However, other scholars theorize geo-culture in relation to power, cross-cultural diplomacy and politics; namely, the appeal to culture, as a soft power tool, in order to exert influence over a given country by reference to cultural symbols, practices and representations. Tim (2019)¹⁵; for instance, argues that geo-culture makes use of the strategic mobilization of an array of aspects of culture, religion and history in order to win friends, build loyalties and legitimize expansions both locally and internationally. For him, geo-culture operates through spatial and cultural resources that go beyond territorial and temporal confines of a given state. Tim provides a very pertinent example exhibiting the manifestation of geo-cultural power—that is China's Silk Road narratives, which reflect the spatial and cultural dimensions of geo-culture used for validating the Chinese geo-political and geo-economic aspirations on a global scale.

As an analytic framework, geo-culture challenges universal theories of culture and civilization—which are deeply anchored in Western cross-cultural narratives and adopts a transformative agenda that condemns any sort of cultural centrism or hegemony foregrounding cross-cultural relations and/ or discourses and any

potential sources of Orientalist thinkings that may continue to hold sway in academic discourse and that may result in reproducing biased narratives of the civilizational other. In so doing, geo-cultural philosophy seeks to indigenize communication research by drawing on the cultural values, traditions, ideas and expressions that fall within a certain cultural or geographic boundary (Wang, 2014)¹⁶; as well as, embraces a culture-centricity as a reference for highlighting cultural and civilizational specificities that are oftentimes subjugated and exploited in cross-cultural relations discourse.

3. Geo-culture and Soft Power: Any Interplay for Soft Cross-Cultural/Civilizational Discourse

The interlock between geo-culture and soft power has been mapped in the literature on international relations (IR) and featured in a series of think tanks publications. In this sense, culture has been regarded as a key asset of soft power discourse whereby countries promote their cultural heritage, achieve their political policies and build mutual relationships across diverse geo-cultural spaces. In such a way, geo-culture and soft power are argued to be part and parcel of inter-cultural discourse and/or hegemony mediation—that is the appeal to cultural aspects to sustain the ascendancy of a given culture in world politics.

The term ‘soft power’ was coined in the early 1990s by the international relations scholar Joseph Nye, who defines it as “the ability to get others to want the outcomes you want through attracting or co-opting them rather than forcing or coercing them” (2004, p. 5)¹⁷. A defining attribute of soft power is that it is non-coercive and cooperative par excellence. For Nye, in today’s multi-polar society, countries foster their foreign policies by dint of three resources: "its culture (in places where it is attractive to others), its political values (when it lives up to them at home and abroad), and its foreign policies (when others see them as legitimate

and having moral authority) (p, 11)”. As a point of illustration, when the culture of a given country entails a set of values and attributes that are disseminated and shared on a global scale, it helps that country in percolating its outlined objectives and orchestrated policies in the target counties. Contrarily, countries whose cultural norms and values are parochial are not likely to be appealing to other culture groups, let alone the dissemination of their foreign policies. The political values or policies are also resources of soft power. For example, the domestic values that a given country projects in its behaviour such as freedom or democracy affect the preferences of others in international contacts. Similarly, when a country’s foreign policies promote universal values such as human rights, liberalism, peace and intercultural pluralism, it affects its diplomatic relations with other countries. These points are succinctly summarized by Nye as follows:

“A country may obtain the outcomes it wants in world politics because other countries—admiring its values, emulating its example, aspiring to its level of prosperity and openness—want to follow it. In this sense, it is also important to set the agenda and attract others in world politics, and not only to force them to change by threatening military force or economic sanctions. This soft power—getting others to want the outcomes that you want--co-opts people rather than coerces them (p.5)”.¹⁸

It worth-mentioning that although soft power is a non-violent form of cross-cultural discourse, yet it is ideologically-informed because it is argued to be inherently part of cultural hegemony. Powerful countries apply it in order to legitimize their political agendas abroad and reinforce their cultural uniformity worldwide. In other words, despite how attractive the three resources of soft power to the cultural other, they should not be taken for granted. These assets of soft power are, to my stance, tantamount to creating a unilateral and asymmetrical model of interaction between states as well as undermining the diversity and

plurality of cultures and civilizations in a time when cross-cultural dialogue and appreciation of cultural differences are of major importance.

The core tenets of soft power outlined so far intersect with geo-culture in a number of ways. Firstly, both concepts converge in terms of goals—that is building mutual diplomatic relations with other cultures/ civilizations via the conduit of culture. Secondly, they seek to generate positive attitudes of one's own country, to promote its image and to strengthen its influence via the vehicle of cultural products and values. Thirdly, they cater for promoting the local cultural products—ideas, history, art, values and tradition on a global scale. In view of these points of intersection, cultivating a discourse of cross-cultural dialogue in international relations remain among the salient goals of both geo-culture and soft power.

4. Mapping Dialogue among Civilizations as a Global Geo-Cultural Discourse 4

The term cross-cultural dialogue across civilizations and cultures occurred in the era of conflicts and confrontations underlying the relations between states. It has been considered as a powerful rhetoric and antidote against the notorious theory of 'Clash of Civilizations'. And so does the theory of geo-culture. In this chapter, the concept of 'Dialogue among Civilizations' is counted as a global political discourse conducive to reinforcing human coexistence and cross-cultural/civilizational pollination in the context of inter-civilizational encounters.

The dialogue between civilizations emerged as an alternative global political discourse to the two powerful theses of the 'end of history' and the 'clash of civilizations' (Petito, Dallmayr, 2009; Tibi, 2012)¹⁹. It was proposed by the President and the Islamic Republic of Iran Mohammed Khatami in 1998s and adopted by the United Nations as a normative framework for the post-multi-polar

world order (Petito, 2007). Indeed, Francis Fukuyama's and Samuel Huntington's theories²⁰ have been the mainstream discourses underlying the politics of post-Cold War international order; both discourses represent the monologue of an essentially Western-centric and liberal world order. On the one hand, Fukuyama contends that world history has reached its end as a dialectical process after the defeat of communism and liberalism represents a mono-civilizational world order centred on a one global polity or model. Within this horizon, the idea of the existence of multi-civilizational polities is no longer valid. Huntington, on the other hand, maintains that conflicts underlying the post-bipolar international society would no longer be ideological but cultural occurring along civilizational fault-lines. In other words, the thesis of the clash of civilizations was advanced as a geo-political map for understanding the new structure of international world which is based on a plurality of civilizations—each of which is trying to map the entire world along its political, cultural and civilizational models. Nonetheless, both theses have received harsh criticism for their infidelity to multi-culturalism and inter-civilizational bridging (Tyler, 2008)²¹. Against these discourses, inter-civilizational dialogue is proposed as a third political discourse that is in support of mutual cross-cultural/ civilizational understanding (Petito, 2007; Dallmayr, 2001). Central to inter-civilizational dialogue paradigm is a dialogical theory proposed by Hans-George Gadamer's (1992: 132, quoted in Dallmayr, *Beyond Orientalism*: xiii) philosophical thinking, which anticipated the idea of a dialogue across civilizations, which he framed as:

“The human solidarity that I envisage is not a global uniformity but unity in diversity. We must learn to appreciate and tolerate pluralities, multiplicities, and cultural differences...Unity in diversity, and not uniformity and hegemony—that is the heritage of Europe. Such unity-in-diversity has to be extended to the whole world—to include Japan, China,

India, and also Muslim cultures. Every culture, every people has something distinctive to offer for the solidarity and welfare of humanity”.²²

Those global solidarities underscored by Gadamer reside at the heart of inter-civilizational dialogue turn in the politics of international relations. This paradigm challenges the politics of cultural/civilizational unilateralism and calls for a rhetoric of multilateralism—which is tantamount to constituting a peaceful, multicultural, and globalized international society organized around the notions of multi-polarity, cross-cultural *jus gentium*, and a comprehensive idea of peace (Dallmayr, 2009). In this connection, Steger (2009)²³ contends that in order to move from an imperial monologue to a dialogue among cultures and civilizations, there is an urgent need for a commitment to cultural pluralism as well as a conscious effort to highlight the contributions of all cultures to the creation of an increasingly global community of communities. This task can only be achieved through fostering geo-cultural and geo-civilizational communications across nations and adopting a dialogical paradigm in the politics inter-civilizational encounters.

It is worth-mentioning that the theory of dialogism in the arena of international relations encompasses a critique of power politics. Khatami (2000) clearly accentuates this idea, contending that:

“We ought to critically examine the prevalent paradigm in international relations based on the discourse of power, and the glorification of might . . . From an ethical perspective, the paradigm of Dialogue among Civilizations requires that we give up the will-to-power and instead appeal to will-to-empathy and compassion. Without the will-to-empathy, compassion and understanding, there would be no hope for the prevalence of order in our world. We ought gallantly to combat this dearth of compassion and empathy in our world. The ultimate goal of Dialogue

among Civilizations is not dialogue in and of itself, but the attainment of empathy and compassion.”²⁴

It is clear that Khatam’s rejection of power politics implies not only the objection of politics that is bereft of cross-cultural consciousness and instead the establishment of the will-to-empathy, but also the idea that ideas, values and norms embedded in cultures and civilizations should inform the whole political apparatus. In such a pursuit, the ultimate goal of dialogue is building avenues for conflict resolution and inter-civilizational peace and coexistence.

On a similar vein, Va’clav Havel, a post-modern dissident playwright, is another outspoken and proponent of dialogue of civilizations (Petito, 2007)²⁵. Speaking from Western intellectual tradition, Havel (1994, p. 168) has provided an insightful analysis on the compelling need for an inter-civilizational dialogue, pointing out that: “the central political task of the final years of this century . . . the creation of a new model of coexistence among the various cultures, peoples, races and religious sphere within a single interconnected civilization”.²⁶ Havel articulates further the idea that today world has entered an era of multipolar and multicultural international society contained in a single civilization. He uses the metaphor of the ‘common room’ to succinctly describe the idea of different cultures living together within a single civilization, which in turn, necessitates a cross-cultural dialogue centred on a genuine openness and the ability to step beyond the confines of our own habits and prejudices.

Another authority that is worth-citing here is Bassam Tibi’s thesis of inter-civilizational bridging as a framework for preventing civilizational clash or what he termed ‘wars of ideas’ in the arena of geopolitical international relations interactions. To Tibi, the amelioration of civilizational conflicts can be conducted through inter-civilizational dialogue—a turn that has become the limelight in the

political theory of international relations communications. Additionally, Tibi perceives inter-civilizational conflicts as emanating from the religionalization of politics and the shrinking of the world brought about globalization. With regard to the religionalization of politics, he focuses on the Islamism (versus Islam), a modern phenomenon, based on an ahistorical ideology whose value-system is non-negotiable, resting on a political claim of Islamic world order. Against this backdrop, Tibi suggests that Muslims should look back to what he terms the actual, “Hellenized” Islam (p. 74) of the medieval era, which embraced civilizational bridging and respect for cultural and religious others. As for globalization, he views it as a concatenation of multiple civilizations with conflicting values. To address these conflicts, civilizations must end ‘war of ideas’ and adopt an inter-civilizational dialogue based on a mutual respect for cultural differences. That said, Tibi also perceives his trend as distinct from Huntington’s thesis of ‘clash of civilizations’, noting that a ‘conflict is not a clash’ because clashes essentialize and promote polarity (p. ix). By contrast, he suggests that there is a need for a shared ‘cross-cultural morality’ for ‘preventing the clash of civilizations’ and to smooth the way for post-bipolar world peace (p,13). Such an inter-civilizational enterprise can be pursued through de-politicization of religion (here he refers to Islamism) and multi-civilization/multi-culturalism of the politics of international relations discourse.

In a nutshell, the main conclusion that can be deduced from the above-mentioned perspectives is that the ultimate goal of a cross-cultural dialogue is to set up a peaceful and just world order in which all world’s histories, values, arts, literature, cultures, civilizations and traditions are called upon for pursuing a mutual understanding and inter-civilizational fertilization. The latter might unfold only when cultural plurality, civilizational diversity and political multi-polarity are

admitted in the international relations affairs. To this effect, since geo-culture underlies the critical stance of this chapter, I argue that it correlates with the dialogical paradigm in certain points. Firstly, both frameworks advocate a cross-cultural dialogue approach to international cultural relations. Secondly, they call on a rhetoric of convergence of civilizations or cross-civilizational bridging that recognizes and values plurality of different cultural traditions in the intercultural relations discourse. Lastly, they stymie the mono-civilizational framework of world order centred around Western values, ideas and hegemonic perceptions and instead endorse a multi-civilizational approach to international world order.

5. Concluding Remarks

As a recapitulation, this chapter advances the contention that geo-cultural paradigm seeks to bridge cultural/ civilizational-fault-lines through engaging in an active politics of dialogue among and between civilizations in the context of inter-civilizational encounters. In so doing, it denounces “mono-civilizationism” and instead acknowledges the inclusion and recognition of other civilizational traditions in the discourse of international relations, in a bid to circumvent civilizational hierarchy/ hegemony. As such, the implications of geo-cultural interventions in cross-cultural/ civilizational communication reside not only in rethinking asymmetrical power relations across cultural boundaries and catering for cross-cultural/civilizational dialogue on a global scale, but also in drawing on insights from under-represented cultures and civilizations in world politics which have worthwhile contributions to cross-civilization pollination. For these purposes, this chapter has provided a conceptual background for the emergence of geo-culture in international relations as a third paradigm reflecting the cultural turn, mapped the interplay between geo-culture and soft power and advocated a

cross-cultural dialogue framework for pursuing a peaceful cross-cultural/civilizational contact.

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